

Factors Militating against Scholarly Communication among Librarians in Public Universities in South-West Nigeria

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Abstract

This study explores factors that hinder scholarly communication among librarians in public universities in South-West Nigeria. A total of 220 copies of the questionnaire were distributed to librarians at seventeen public universities in South-West Nigeria, of which 203 were duly completed and returned. This represents 92.3% of the questionnaires distributed across the seventeen public universities used for the study. The results indicated that factors such as lack of funds had the highest percentage score (yes = 90.1%), followed by high cost of publication (89.2%), erratic power supply (88.7%), strict work schedule (86.8%), lack of time due to library routine (86.3%), inadequate research infrastructure (85.7%), and lack of orientation among librarians (84.2%). The study recommended that essential and appropriate ICT equipment should be made available by the administration of both federal and state universities to advance librarians' scholarly communication in public universities in South-West Nigeria.

Keywords: Scholarly communication, Librarians, public Universities, ICT

Introduction

Universities, as institutions of higher education, are a nation's intellectual strongholds, serving as both incubators of new ideas and archival repositories of historical fact. "There are five main objectives of a university: teaching, research, dissemination of existing and new information, pursuit of service to the community, and a storehouse of knowledge" (National University Commission, 2022, p.1). Eruanga (2021) also emphasised that the university's primary mission is to convey knowledge, enhance individuals' mindsets, and add to the body of knowledge. According to Ifijeh, Ogbomo, and Ifijeh (2018), the growth and development of a nation's productive sectors are significantly aided by research conducted at universities and other higher-education institutions. Javed, Ahmad, and Khahro (2020) also emphasised that universities and degree-awarding institutes contribute significantly to a country's higher education and development.

As Jaffe et al. (2020) indicate, scholarly communication has been linked to a country's intellectual and economic wealth. Mahar and Quiliam (2018) emphasised that one outcome of scholarly communication is the publication of findings. Scholarly communication is regarded as a crucial indicator of an institution's standing and has become an alternative measure of the quality of teaching and course offerings in today's fiercely competitive global education market (Byrne, 2017). Weng'ua et al. (2018) reported that the number of journal articles published by a university's faculty is used to determine the university's ranking, and the number of scholarly articles published by faculty members is considered during appointment and promotion processes. The academic community as a whole agrees that academic research should produce high-quality output that is published in an acceptable format after a thorough peer-review process and made available in print or electronic formats, such as conference papers and proceedings, books

(monographs), theses and dissertations, chapters in books, articles in scholarly journals, patents and trademarks, as well as creative works such as exhibitions and performances. McGrail et al. (2016) affirmed that "publish or perish" has long been used to evaluate faculty members' performance, particularly in relation to promotion, salary increases, and contract renewal. Similarly, Omoluabi-Idiodi (2019) corroborated this assertion, noting that the phrase "publish or perish" emphasises the importance placed on research output in any university, as research publications are a significant indicator of an academic's efforts and a driver of their academic career prospects.

Elimna (2016) also observed that academics worldwide place a premium on research and publication, not only because it is assumed to enrich teaching and learning and add to the body of knowledge, but also because it plays a major role in establishing the reputation of a given institution. Thus, scholarly communication serves the dual purpose of enhancing both one's own position and the institution's status for academic staff. Producing new knowledge through research increases an institution's prestige, encourages technological advancement and innovation, raises the calibre of its faculty, and boosts its financial status (Dhilon et al., 2015). Academics' ability to disseminate their findings and garner respect from their colleagues depends heavily on their ability to get their work published. Thus, the visibility of researchers and their institutions increases due to their published work (Rawat & Meena, 2014).

Scholarly communication remains a high priority for many librarians. Promoting librarians to academic positions is a standard practice at universities worldwide. It began in the 1940s in America and then spread to the United Kingdom and Canada in the 1980s. In the United States and Canada, academic librarians are often criticised for not publishing enough research to advance in their careers or earn tenure (Sassen & Wahl, 2014). As Igbokwe et al. (2019) argue, promoting librarians in university libraries from one level to another requires publishing multiple articles in both local and international journals and presenting papers at local and international conferences. In the United States, academic librarians are often accorded the same status as faculty members and are subject to the same publication requirements for tenure and advancement as other academic faculty (Hoffmann et al., 2014). Given the importance of scholarly publication, the Indian government invests approximately 1% of GDP in research and development (Bachalapur & Jayaprakash, 2014). The academic status of university librarians in Sri Lanka has contributed significantly to the development of the profession. Thus, librarians cannot simply avoid the promotion requirements as their teaching counterparts have (Ayasundara, 2011).

According to Lamptey and Boshoff (2019), librarians in Ghana are under constant pressure to "publish or perish" yet are overwhelmed by library duties. The authors further stated that, to fulfil their research and publication missions, academic librarians need to engage in two distinct forms of work: conducting primary research and disseminating secondary research. Omanga (2017) decried the tragedy of Kenya's vanishing scholars. He reaffirmed his earlier claims that the vast majority of Kenyan academics follow the "publish or perish" model, prioritising quantity targets and publishing in predatory outlets without hesitation. Meanwhile, he stressed that this is not expected, as scholarly work and publication need to follow a career pattern. Kilonzo and Kitche (2014) stressed that Kenyan academics are unable to do as much research as their counterparts in developed nations due to excessive workloads, limited pay, and competing demands from teaching, consulting, research, and publication responsibilities. Low levels of research output in Africa's higher education institutions have been confirmed by Jaffe et al. (2020), Elimna (2016), and Uwizeye et al. (2022). It seems that the number of aspiring academics and researchers in sub-Saharan Africa is already outpacing the favourable conditions, resources, and research opportunities available to them (Beaudry, Mouton, & Prozesky, 2018). Africa contributes only 2 per cent to the world's total research output, and sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) contributes less than 1 per cent to global research efforts (Siyao et al., 2017).

In Nigeria, librarians in libraries and related fields are among the privileged few who hold academic positions, such as lecturers and instructors, at post-secondary institutions (Benson et al., 2017). After a prolonged industrial action by the Academic Staff Union of Universities in Nigeria, the Nigerian government and the Union finally settled their differences in 1993. Following the agreement, librarians in Nigerian universities now have the same status as their teaching counterparts. As reported by Omoluabi-Idiodi (2012), this accord ended a period during which librarians in Nigerian university libraries had claimed academic status. However, with their expanded roles, they are now expected to produce high-quality research that demonstrates they deserve a place in the academic community. To level the playing field between lecturers and librarians, the National University Commission (NUC) instituted a new policy in 1990, as mandated by Decree 16. For librarians to succeed in their careers at Nigerian universities, they must produce as many articles as lecturers. According to Okonedo (2015), librarians have accepted the need to conduct original research and publish the results in peer-reviewed publications, just as their teaching counterparts do.

The quantity and quality of a librarian's research output are strong indicators of their academic standing and prospects for promotion, recognition, and career advancement. In modern Nigeria, librarians are mostly judged for promotion on the number and quality of scholarly articles published in peer-reviewed journals and conference proceedings. According to Benson, Amaechi, and Onuoha (2017), academic librarians engage in research as part of the requirements for achieving the status accorded to them in the academic environment. Given the importance of research and publication across all fields, academic librarians at universities globally are not exempt from conducting their own research (Ocholla et al., 2012). As Chauhan and Mahajan (2017) point out, librarians are obliged by the established order to make significant contributions to expanding the body of knowledge in their field. This means they must conduct scholarly research and disseminate their findings through scholarly journals. Librarians have become indispensable workers in Nigeria's higher education institutions, serving as guardians of information (Adetayo et al., 2022). Badmus-Adegbite (2022) reiterated that, in librarianship, scholarly communication is highly significant because it enhances librarians' reputation within the academic community.

Statement of the Problem

Scholarly communication is one of the requirements for career progression for all academic staff, including librarians in Nigerian universities. It is generally measured by the number of scholarly publications, including journal articles, books, book chapters, monographs, book reviews, and conference proceedings. Many librarians have made little progress in research and publication (Tsafe et al., 2016). According to Basiru (2018), librarians are less productive than lecturers or other academic staff, and their research frequently ranks low among academics. Librarians are not uniformly enthusiastic about or skilled at creating and maintaining scholarly records. Librarians lack a well-established research culture. This is evidenced by the low level of scholarly publications among librarians in Nigerian universities.

Compared with the number of publications associated with librarians, the citation counts of six librarians from the South-South zone are extremely low, as reported by Orji et al. (2019). This suggests that librarians' scholarly publications have little influence on the academic community. Their findings also indicate a low level of research output, as the h-index is calculated through citation analysis. Librarians' historically low publication output, compared with other academic staff, affects their chances of advancement and career progression. On this premise, the study is being carried out to investigate the challenges of scholarly communication among librarians in public universities in the Southwest, Nigeria.

Literature Review

Scholarly communication is often assessed by the quality and quantity of scholarly outputs produced within a given period (Bada, Daramola and Oga, 2024). According to Orji and Anunobi (2019), researchers in the field of library and information science rely heavily on scholarly publications to disseminate their findings and to gauge the merits of potential hiring and promotion. Therefore, to plan their work effectively, librarians are expected to teach, conduct research, and communicate research findings, in addition to completing other administrative tasks. Tsafe et al. (2016) emphasise that academic librarians who engage in research and publication are better equipped to adapt to new situations and to foster positive working relationships with other academic staff. Ocholla et al. (2012) and Fennewald (2008) also state that academic librarians conduct research and publish for career benefits, such as status enhancement, promotion, securing tenure or permanent appointment, acquiring recognition for creative thinking, visibility, and acceptability both inside and outside the university community, and satiating intellectual curiosity. In Nigeria, promotional factors for librarians place a premium on the number and quality of their scholarly output, which takes the form of articles published in journals, conference presentations, and other scholarly venues (Okonedo et al., 2015). Research has shown that librarians' scholarly publications are low in Nigeria, although universities require scholarly publications from all librarians (Adamu, 2022). The majority of librarians express frustration with the challenge of producing journal articles for publication in reputable journals. Igere (2020) remarked that the scholarly publication of librarians has been exceptionally low in recent years.

Librarians' insufficient scholarly communication has slowed career advancement, including status enhancement, promotion, or permanent appointment, and has hindered recognition, visibility, and acceptance both within and outside the university community. Ezeani et al. (2018) identified several factors that hinder librarians' scholarly communication, including: difficulty in writing a high-quality, acceptable article for an impact-factor-rated journal; extremely high publishing costs; a lack of institutional support and mentorship; and a lack of support from non-governmental organisations.

Fabunmi (2022) conducted a study on how librarians at private universities in South-West Nigeria use print and non-print resources as determinants of scholarly communication. Librarians were given 120 copies of the questionnaire, of which 109 were returned, yielding a 90.8% response rate. The main obstacles to librarians' research output were the high cost of internet access, the lack of a research focus, and the expense of publications.

Helio, da Silva, and Abi (2026) conducted a study on the issues faculty encountered in improving scholarly publication at the Dili Institute of Technology, Timor-Leste. Consequently, the relationship between problems in embarking on research and lecturers' preparedness to do so was examined through correlation analysis using SPSS. The results indicated that the overall mean score for improving willingness to conduct research was 4.51, the maximum mean score, followed by a shortage of research training, with a mean score of 3.61, indicating significant challenges to research productivity.

Igiri et al. (2021) conducted a study focusing on the challenges and productivity of researchers in Nigerian academic institutions without funding. 42.98% reported a lack of research funding, 17.11% cited the brain drain, and 8.85% indicated a lack of motivation. Fiawotoafor (2021) examined scholarly publication among professional librarians in four public universities in Ghana. The findings revealed that a lack of time and a heavy workload, an inflexible work schedule, and the absence of a formal mentoring programme were obstacles to the scholarly publication activities of the professional librarians.

Objective of the Study

The main objective of this study was to:

- i. Find out the extent of scholarly communication among librarians in public universities in South-West Nigeria.
- ii. Find out factors militating against scholarly communication among librarians in public universities in South- West Nigeria.

Research Methodology

In this study, a descriptive survey was employed as the research method. Nworgu (2006) defines survey research as "any research that examines a population or set of conditions through data collection and analysis from a sample size that is supposed to be representative of the whole". The population of this study comprised 220 librarians in public universities in South-West Nigeria. This category of library staff was chosen because they are academic in status and are expected to conduct research and publish reports of their findings in the form of journal articles, books, book chapters, monographs, book reviews, conference proceedings, and patents to support academic development and promotion. Given the manageable population size, the research employed complete enumeration. Total enumeration techniques allow researchers to avoid biased samples. It guarantees a high degree of accuracy in data collection when the population is not too large. Copies of the questionnaire were distributed to respondents in the study area, and the response rate was calculated based on the total number of copies collected. A total of 220 copies of the questionnaire were distributed to seventeen federal and state public university librarians in South-West Nigeria; however, 203 were duly completed and returned. This represents 92.3% of the total questionnaires distributed. The study used frequency counts and percentages as statistical measures for data analysis. The research questions formed the basis for data analysis.

Research Question 1: What is the extent of librarians’ scholarly communication in public universities in South-West Nigeria between 2020 and 2025?

Table 1 Librarians’ Scholarly Communication

S/N	Scholarly Communication	1-5 times	5-10 times	11-15 times	More than 15 times
1	Chapters in books	42(20.7%)	43(21.9%)	66 (32.5%)	52 (24.7%)
2	Journal articles	51 (25.1%)	38 (18.7%)	46 (22.7%)	68 (33.5%)
3	Conference paper presentation	67 (33 %)	66(32.5%)	41(20.2%)	29 (14.3%)
4	Seminal papers	89 (43.8%)	38 (18.7%)	41 (20.2%)	35 (17.2%)
5	Edited book published	90 (44.3%)	43 (21.9%)	50 (24.6%)	20 (10.2%)
6	Technical Reports	72(35.5%)	44(21.7%)	32 (15.8%)	55 (27%)

Table 1 shows the extent to which the following research resources contributes to librarians scholarly communication where 32.5% of the study participants indicated that chapters in books had contributed to scholarly communication among librarians 1- 5 times, while 33.5% stated that Journal article were consulted more than 15 times by Librarians, 33% of the respondents have consulted conference paper presentation, also 43.8% stated that on the range of 1 – 5 times, Librarians have consulted seminal papers,

44.3% also stated that they have consulted edited books. 35.5% have used technical reports, which improve scholarly communication.

Research Question 2: What are the factors militating against scholarly communication among librarians in public universities in South-West, Nigeria?

Table 2: Factors Militating against Librarians' Scholarly Communication

Factors	Number	Frequency	Percentage
Lack of fund	90.1	9.9	100%
High cost of publication	89.2	10.8	100%
Lack of electricity supply	88.7	11.3	100%
Strict work schedule	86.8	13.2	100%
Lack of time due to library work	86.8	13.2	100%
Lack of orientation among librarians	85.7	14.3	100%
Absence of mentorship	82.8	17.2	100%
lack of a favourable environment	82.3	17.7	100%
High cost of internet access	81.3	18.7	100%
Lack of support from senior colleagues	77.3	22.7	100%
Lack of research direction	75.4	24.6	100%

Results and Discussion

Responses to research question 1 above show the extent to which the following research resources contribute to librarians’ scholarly communication. 32.5% of the study participants indicated that chapters in books had contributed to scholarly communication among librarians 1–5 times, while 33.5% stated that librarians had consulted journal articles more than 15 times. 33% of respondents consulted conference paper presentations. 43.8% stated that, on a scale of 1–5, librarians consulted seminal papers, and 44.3% also stated that they consulted edited books. 35.5% have used technical reports, which improve scholarly communication.

Responses to research question 2 indicate that lack of funds had the highest percentage (yes = 90.1%), followed by high cost of publication (89.2%), erratic power supply (88.7%), strict work schedule (86.8%), lack of time due to library routine (86.3%), inadequate research infrastructure (85.7%), and lack of orientation among librarians (84.2%). By implication, the key challenges to the research output of librarians in public universities in South-West, Nigeria, include lack of funds, high cost of publication, erratic power supply, strict work schedule, lack of time due to library routine, inadequate research infrastructure, lack of orientation among librarians, absence of mentorship, absence of a favourable environment, high cost of internet access, lack of support from senior colleagues, and absence of research direction. Findings align with Pillai (2014), Ighan and Khan (2017), Agbo et al. (2020), Shastri and Chudasman (2021), Eliezer and Enuma (2021), Pallain (2014), Igiri et al. (2021), Moses and Onwukajo (2022), and Fabunmi (2022), which identify the major factors militating against scholarly communication among librarians as lack of funds, high cost of publication, erratic power supply, strict work schedule, lack of time due to library routine, inadequate research infrastructure, lack of orientation among librarians, lack of mentorship, absence of a favourable environment, high cost of internet access, lack of support from senior colleagues, and absence of research direction.

The study revealed that the research resources that contributed to librarians’ scholarly communication were mainly journal articles, co-edited books, conference paper presentations, and technical reports. The key challenges to scholarly communication among librarians in public universities in South-West, Nigeria

are lack of funds, high cost of publication, erratic power supply, strict work schedules, lack of time due to library routines, inadequate research infrastructure, lack of orientation among librarians, absence of mentorship, absence of a favourable environment, high cost of internet access, lack of support from senior colleagues, and absence of research direction.

Conclusion

Librarians, as part of the academic subsystem, are required to produce and publish high-quality research, which will ultimately benefit their careers. Igbokwe, Benson, and Enem (2019) stated that advancing in the ranks of a university library requires several publications in peer-reviewed journals, as well as conference presentations on both national and international platforms. There are major factors militating against scholarly communication among librarians in public universities in the South-West of Nigeria, and these factors warrant serious consideration and attention. African universities are making strides towards removing internal and external obstacles to scholarly communication, and these initiatives are encouraging. To facilitate researchers' contributions to Africa's development agenda, the leadership of higher education institutions must emphasise research funding.

Recommendations

The following were recommended from the findings of the study

1. Research findings by librarians should be subjected to peer review by learned colleagues before being submitted for publication.
2. Librarians in public universities in South-West Nigeria should aim to publish more textbooks, journal articles, conference proceedings, monographs, book chapters, and technical reports in high-rated journals to increase visibility.

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